

Influence of Location and Type of School on School Environment of High School Students

Education

KEYWORDS : School Environment, Government School Students, Private Students, Rural and Urban

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ABSTRACT

The study was intended to investigate the influence of location and type of school on school environment of high school students. To achieve this purpose, 100 high school students were selected from various schools from Tenkasi Taluk of Tirunelveli District of Tamilnadu. As the problem selected for the present study is concerned with one of the main issues, after reviewing the characteristics of the different methods of educational research, the investigator has employed descriptive method using survey as a technique for the present study. The investigator used the stratified random sampling technique for selecting the sample. In the present investigation, to measure school environment of high school students, School Environment Scale developed and validated by the investigators. The result revealed that the urban school students have better school environment than the rural school students. Further comparing on the basis of type of school, both the government and private high school students do not differ significantly in their school environment.

Introduction

John Dewey says “School is a special environment, where a certain quality of the lie and certain types of activities and occupations are provided with the object of security the child’s development along desirable lines”. Environment is a general term designating all the subjects, forces, and conditions that affect the individual through such stimuli as he able to receive. The learning environment refers to school environment. Only a few children enjoy the blessings of all the environment. School Environment is an external factor and teacher- student relations is an internal factor. These two factors basically decide the process of teaching and learning. The values among teachers decide and control both the factors. Child spends most of the time at the school interacting with the school environment. Hence it stands as one of the basic factors of learning. The school is a factor of tremendous importance in education. The more the emphasis on speeding up the learning process, the more will be the emphasis on good learning environment. Non-functional, meagerly equipped and unattractively decorated school plants have given place to plants with superior lighting ,attractive decoration, comfortable seating ,useful service facilities such as library, multipurpose room, functional playgrounds, and class-rooms with chalk and boards, sinks, work areas, filing and storage facilities and pupils’ lockers. A school’s physical environment includes the school building and the surrounding grounds, such as noise, temperature, and lighting as well as physical, biological, or chemical agents. The psychosocial school environment encompasses the attitudes, feelings, and values of students and staff. Physical and psychological safety, positive interpersonal relationships, recognition of the needs and success of the individual, and support for learning are all part of the psychosocial environment. Creating a healthy school environment requires the involvement of virtually everyone in the school—students, administrators, teachers, custodial and maintenance staff, school counsellors, school nurses, nutrition services workers.

Significance of the Study

India is one of the largest countries of the world with diverse population both in geographical and cultural terms. Only 27% of village schools in India have electricity compared to 76% of schools in towns and cities. Only about half of the rural schools surveyed have enough toilets for girls, and fewer than 4% have a telephone, according to a new global report by UNESCO on the impact of social inequality on the quality of education. In general, village schools are in greater need of repair, according to the survey. The debate on whether private schools provide a better quality primary education as compared to government schools is heating up in India. This is completely understandable in the current scenario. On the one hand, for almost ten years, through Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, the government has intensified the move towards universalizing elementary education and more

recently the Right to Education Bill has been passed in the Parliament. This push has led to impressive increases in provision and enrolment. On the other hand, ASER as well as other data show a clear rising trend in private school enrolment in rural India. The school atmosphere, the school environment should be an abode of health. There should be good physical condition prevailing in the school consisting of proper sanitation, supply of pure drinking water, provision for mid-day meal and play ground of reasonable dimension. For the best emotional, social and personal health of the pupils, a healthful school environment is necessary. Creative self expression is emphasized in school. An atmosphere conducive to self expression along all lines is created for the pupil. The child is given every opportunity for developing ability to express himself in any worthy way that he may wish. The social, cultural and political context of a country or a region affects its schools and classrooms. The environment of a school in India would naturally reflect the attitudes and mentality of the wider culture of which it is a component. Based to a large extent on the socio-cultural values of tradition and respect, the typical Indian school environment has a teacher who is a figure of authority, commanding respect, and the typical student is one who learns quietly and passively. Our Prime Minister Manmohan Singh said the school environment should be “free from fear, trauma and anxiety” to make the Right to Education (RTE) a grand national movement. “The RTE Act bans corporal punishment and mental harassment. It also bans detention and expulsion. These provisions have led many teachers to question how discipline will be maintained in the classroom,” he said. Successfully managing a school environment is a necessary and essential educational investment. Facility management systems determine environmental quality in schools. The quality of the school environment shapes attitudes of students, teachers and staff. Attitudes affect teaching and learning behavior. Behavior affects performance. Educational performance determines future outcomes of individuals and society as a whole. With this background, the present study explores the effect of location and type of school on school environment of high school students.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the level of school environment of high school students with regard to location of school and type of school.
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference between rural and urban high school students in their school environment.
3. To find out whether there is any significant difference between government and private high school students in their school environment.

Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in school environment of high school students with respect to locality of school.
2. There is no significant difference in school environment of high school students with respect to type of school.

Method

As the problem selected for the present study is concerned with one of the main issues, after reviewing the characteristics of the different methods of educational research, the investigator has employed descriptive method using survey as a technique for the present study.

Sample

A Sample of 100 high school students from Tenkasi Taluk of Tirunelveli District of Tamilnadu was taken in the present study. The sample were taken from 5 schools (class IX and X). The investigator used the stratified random sampling technique for selecting the sample.

Tools Used for the Present Study

In the present investigation to measure school environment of high school students, School Environment Scale developed and validated by the Investigators.

Statistical Techniques Used

Information gathered was put to suitable statistical treatment by using Mean, SD and t- test.

Analysis of data

The data was analyzed in the light of hypothesis designed for the study.

Table 1.01
Level of School Environment of high school students with regard to locality and type of school

Variable	Background Variable		Low		Average		High	
			Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
School Environment	Location of School	Rural	20	33.3	32	53.3	8	13.3
		Urban	6	15	16	40	18	45
	Type of school	Govt.	10	20	25	50	15	30
		Private	16	32	23	46	11	22

From the above table it is clear that most of the high school students have average level of school environment with regard to the location of school and type of school.

Null Hypothesis: 1

There is no significant difference in school environment of high school students with respect to location of school.

Table 1.02
t-test showing the significant difference in School Environment of high school students with respect to locality of school

Variable	Location of School	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't' value	Remarks
School Environment	Rural	60	389.8333	49.94952	4.365	S
	Urban	40	434.9000	51.52037		

(t=1.96 at 5% level of significance)

It is inferred from the above table that, the calculated t-value (4.365) is greater than table value (1.96) for df (100) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant difference in school environment of high school students with respect to location of school.

Null Hypothesis: 2

There is no significant difference in school environment of high school students with respect to type of school.

Table 1.03
t-test showing the significant difference in School Environment of high school students with respect to type of school

Variable	Type of school	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated 't' value	Remarks
School Environment	Govt.	50	416.8400	58.11297	0.167	NS
	Private	50	398.8800	50.69381		

It is inferred from the above table that, the calculated t-value (0.167) is less than table value (1.96) for df (100) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is no significant difference in school environment of high school students with respect to type of school.

Findings and Interpretation

On the basis of results obtained after the Interpretation of Objectives and Hypotheses, the following findings have been drawn:

- o From the descriptive analysis, it is found that only 13% of rural high school students have high level of school environment, but 45% of urban high school students have high level of students. Moreover majority of sample have shown moderate level of school environment with respect to location of school.
- o And also from the percentage analysis, the investigator found that 30% of government high school students have high level of school environment but only 22% of private high school students have high level of school students. Most of the high school students have average level of school environment.
- o From Inferential analysis, It is also found that there exists significant difference in the mean scores of school environment of rural and urban high school students. The urban school students have better school environment than the rural school students. It may be due to the fact that the most of the rural high schools are run by government. At present, the government high schools have shortage in teachers and also have poor infrastructure facilities. Poor infrastructure, untrained teachers and pitiable classroom interaction in the rural high schools may become the source of low school environment among rural high school students.
- o It is also found that both the government and private high school students do not differ significantly in their school environment. It may be due to the effect of equitable education(Samacheer Kalvi). Because in all the matriculation and state board schools and all the private and government high schools in Tamilnadu, same syllabus belong to samacheer kalvi system is utilized. And also the evaluation system(Continuous and Comprehensive Evaluation System) is also same for both private and government schools.

Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed that high school students from urban high schools showed better school environment than that of high school students from rural high school students. Schools in rural areas face difficult challenges in serving the needs of children and public education. Many rural schools lack the funding needed to improve the quality of their school environment and give the students the resources they need to succeed. It is obvious that without extra government funding many rural schools will continue to struggle with meeting their students' needs. So the government should conduct a site assessment of the rural schools physical and social environment frequently to determine the rural school's needs. The central and state governments actively support the development of

programmes that recognize and deal with the particular needs of high school students, educators, school employees and communities in the nation's vast rural areas. A school's environment is the thread that connects the multitude of activities on a campus. In many respects this thread is almost invisible, yet everyone experiences its influence. Positive social relationships and attitudes about school are as important to the environment as are safe and well-kept buildings and grounds. A safe, clean, and well-maintained school with a positive psychosocial climate and culture can foster and boost student and staff health as well as students' educational achievement. School administrators have the overall responsibility for a school's physical and psychosocial environment. Superintendents have the responsibility for complying with laws, rules, and education code sections that affect the school environment. Teachers and supervisors need

to spend a considerable amount of time in providing school climate. With an improved school climate, pupils should learn more than previously. A climate which is conducive to optimizing learner achievement is a must. A negative school climate hinders pupils from achieving and may well also develop inappropriate attitudes. The government will have to provide a large number of new schools in the rural areas and also arrange for more enrolment in the existing rural schools. The school environment is also very important for the school going students. The school will not lay emphasis on what is to be learnt but on what is to be learnt but on what the learner demands to learn. If mankind or children in school can be free from institutional restraints then their natural talents and capabilities will come forth. Children are basically creative and interested in learning, when given freedom and creative environment.

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